

Verification of a Pin-Wise Modelling Approach for the BME TR's Distorted Lattices using FENNECS with HELIOS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the verification of a high-resolution, pin-by-pin neutronics model for the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) Training Reactor (TR), developed within the EURATOM project EVEREST. The core features six distinct fuel assembly types with distorted pin lattices, necessitating a custom polygon-based meshing approach for the FENNECS diffusion/ SP_3 solver. A 2D HELIOS-2 lattice model was first verified against a high-fidelity SERPENT 2 Monte Carlo reference, achieving a k_{eff} difference of 104 pcm and an RMS pin power error of 1.19%. The study investigates the impact of energy group structure and homogenization level (pin-wise vs. assembly-wise) on deterministic transport accuracy. Results indicate that using more than 2 energy groups is critical for accurately modeling the strong spectral gradients at the core-reflector interface. Furthermore, the SP_3 transport approximation combined with pin-wise homogenization significantly reduces error compared to diffusion theory. The methodology is applied to a 3D full-core FENNECS model, yielding an assembly power distribution RMS error of 0.94%, an integral fuel rod power MARE of 1.47%, and a k_{eff} bias of approximately -217 pcm against a 3D SERPENT reference. The results demonstrate that the pin-wise model successfully captures local flux peaking in specific void and water channel regions that are physically smoothed out in homogenized models.

Keywords: FENNECS, HELIOS-2, BME Training Reactor, Pin-wise modelling, Distorted Lattice

1. INTRODUCTION

This research was conducted within the framework of the EURATOM project EVEREST (Experiments for Validation and Enhancement of Reactor Pressure Vessel Fluence Assessment). The core objective of the EVEREST project is to demonstrate the usefulness and trustworthiness of advanced multi-physics simulation platforms for assessing core internals and reactor pressure vessel fluence, validating these computational tools through the production of dedicated experimental data. This paper contributes to the project's technical goals aligned with the neutronics analysis by providing conventional and higher fidelity neutronics modelling that serves as a foundation for future high-fidelity multiphysics models of research reactors. This study focuses on developing these models for the 100 kW nominal power Training Reactor (TR) at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) [1], one of the facilities utilized in the project's experimental validation axis. A comprehensive review detailing the project's methodology, its application to VVER reactors, and its synergies with the related CAMIVVER and DELISA-LTO projects is provided in Hursin et al. (2025) [2].

This paper describes the development of a 2-D pin-by-pin neutron transport model of the BME TR for future use in a 3-D model in the coupled code system FENNECS/CTF. The Finite ElemeNt NeutroniCS

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(FENNECS) code, developed at GRS and included in the 2023 AC2 package [3], is a geometrically flexible solver designed for multi-physics safety assessments [4, 5]. It utilizes the Finite Element Method (FEM) to solve the three-dimensional, few-group steady-state and time-dependent diffusion equations. Initially based on a Continuous Galerkin method, it has recently been extended to include the Simplified P3 (SP_3) transport method [6, 7] and a Discontinuous Galerkin approach to address power tilts observed in thermal systems [4]. FENNECS reads macroscopic cross-section libraries in a NEMTAB-like format, which allows for parametrization against various thermal-hydraulic feedback parameters. For meshing its complex geometries, FENNECS employs the Python External Meshing Tool (PEMTY), which generates the required mesh data from a Yaml input. This tool's ability to mesh arbitrary polygons is highly relevant for modelling the irregular lattice pin cells of the BME TR. As a prerequisite for high-fidelity multiphysics simulations at pin-cell and subchannel resolution, the subsequent sections outline the BME TR assembly characteristics, the generation of pin cell-wise homogenized few-group cross section (XS) libraries using HELIOS-2 (2.04.01), and finally, the FENNECS pin-by-pin model and its qualification using HELIOS-2 and SERPENT 2.

2. THE BME TR CORE AND HIGH-RESOLUTION MESHING STRATEGY

The BME TR is a light water moderated and cooled pool-type reactor, first commissioned in 1971 with an initial nominal power of 10 kW and upgraded to its current 100 kW thermal power in 1980. Located at the Central Campus of BME, its primary purpose is training engineers and physicists, though it also serves in scientific research and industrial projects. The reactor core is located at the bottom of a 6-meter-high cylindrical vessel and consists of 24 EK-10 fuel assemblies (FAs), which contain nominally 10% enriched UO_2 in a metal magnesium matrix. These assemblies are surrounded by 41 solid graphite reflector blocks, and the entire assembly is submerged in demineralized water. The facility provides extensive experimental capabilities, including several vertical irradiation channels, horizontal beam tubes, a large irradiation tunnel, and a pneumatic sample-delivery (rabbit) system. Notably, the reactor has not been refueled since its commissioning, with an estimated total released thermal energy of approximately 18.8 MWdays. The technical data for the modelling were taken from [8]. The reactor serves as a valuable benchmark for steady-state reactor physics, with recent studies focusing on validating conventional assembly-wise modelling approaches using diffusion, SP_3 and discrete ordinates codes against high-fidelity Monte Carlo simulations (SERPENT 2) and experimental measurements [9, 10].

Figure 1. BME TR Core Midplane Layout. Note the distorted pin arrangements in FA Types 21, 52, and 6 near the control rod positions (a, m, s). (Adapted from [8])

2.1. Algebraic Meshing Algorithm for Irregular Lattices

The core is highly heterogeneous, featuring six FA types (Fig. 1). While Type 1 is a regular 17×17 mm square lattice, Types 21 and 52 feature "cut corners" to accommodate control rods, resulting in distorted pin positions. Type 6 is further modified for the pneumatic rabbit system.

Standard homogenization techniques using rectangular grids are ill-suited for these distorted lattices. Consequently, a polygon-based unstructured mesh is required to explicitly represent the pin locations while taking into account the shroud and corner cuts. While a Voronoi tessellation is the standard mathematical solution for defining polygons in irregular lattices [11], it generates strictly convex polygons with varying numbers of edges. This geometric irregularity complicates the generation of connection operators required by HELIOS, which favors structured inputs [12].

To address this, a novel algebraic meshing algorithm was developed specifically for this work, which utilizes a direct algebraic approach based on the logical $n \times n$ pin grid. This ensures a fixed number of edges for each pin-cell, maintaining the structural regularity required for easier modelling while representing the lattice distortions.

The algorithm generates the pin-cell polygon vertices for a pin at logical index m by explicitly identifying its neighbors in the logical grid:

1. **Orthogonal Vertices:** Four vertices are placed at the midpoints of the vectors connecting pin m to its direct orthogonal neighbors ($m \pm 1, m \pm n$).
2. **Diagonal Vertices:** The remaining four vertices are determined by the local diagonals. For each 2×2 logical pin group sharing a corner, the algorithm calculates the two diagonal vectors spanning the group (e.g., $\vec{v}_1 = \vec{p}_{m+n+1} - \vec{p}_m$ and $\vec{v}_2 = \vec{p}_{m+n} - \vec{p}_{m+1}$). A vertex is placed at the midpoint of the **shorter** diagonal.

This logic ensures that the resulting mesh effectively "wraps" around the pins, generating consistent octagonal cells for all interior positions.

The algorithm handles assembly boundaries by mapping vertices to the aluminum shroud geometry. For the more complex Type 21, 52 and 6 assemblies, the "cut corner" shroud geometry is assigned to the corner pin-cells (see Fig. 2). Finally, to satisfy HELIOS-2 requirements, the mesh is internally refined by generating 16 additional sub-nodes per cell: 8 defining the cladding and 8 bisecting the moderator region to capture self-shielding effects.

Figure 2. Consistent Mesh Generation for FA Type 6: (a) Algebraic generation of cell vertices (green), shroud (blue and green) and assembly boundaries (red); (b) Resulting HELIOS-2 mesh with internal pin-cell refinement; (c) Corresponding FENNECS unstructured mesh (triangulated).

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The analysis is divided into three stages to systematically isolate error sources: (1) verification of the HELIOS-2 lattice physics model against Monte Carlo reference; (2) a 2D sensitivity study on energy groups and transport approximations using FENNECS; and (3) a final 3D full-core verification.

3.1. Verification of the HELIOS-2 Reference Model

To establish a reliable source for homogenized cross-sections, a 2D full-core HELIOS-2 model was verified against a high-fidelity SERPENT 2 Monte Carlo reference [9]. The reference calculation was performed with 100,000 active cycles of 50,000 particles (5×10^9 active histories) using continuous-energy ENDF/B-VII.0 libraries at 300.0 K, yielding a reference k_{eff} of $1.10413 \pm 2.4 \times 10^{-5}$. The verification compared two deterministic solvers: Method of Characteristics (MoC) and Collision Probability (CP), utilizing an internal 56-group nuclear data library based on ENDF/B-VII.

The MoC solver proved superior, achieving a k_{eff} difference of +104 pcm and an RMS pin power error of 1.19%, compared to 1.37% for the faster CP solver (53 min vs. 553 min). Crucially, the MoC solution reduced the maximum pin power error from 4.95% to 3.69% and yielded a Power Peaking Factor (PPF) of 1.373 (vs. reference 1.342).

The spatial error distribution (Figure 3) reveals distinct error modes driven by geometry and material interfaces. The deterministic model systematically overestimates power near the air-filled beam tubes due to the simplified representation of streaming effects, while underestimating power at the graphite and moderator reflector edge. Additionally, the maximum peaking error is structurally driven, located at the corner pin adjacent to the pneumatic rabbit system in assembly D5. The simplified geometric representation of this irregular, air-filled void in the deterministic model leads to an overestimation of the local flux peaking compared to the explicit Monte Carlo geometry.

Figure 3. Verification of the reference model: (Left) Spatial distribution of relative pin power error (HELIOS-2 vs. SERPENT); (Right) Normalized SERPENT pin power distribution showing the core layout.

3.2. Energy Group Structure Selection

A critical parameter for the FENNECS model is the energy group structure. Initial scoping calculations using a standard 2-group structure ($E_{cut} = 0.625$ eV) resulted in unacceptable errors (k_{eff} deviations > 2500 pcm) when the graphite reflector was explicitly modeled. The standard thermal group is too broad to resolve the strong spectral softening that occurs at the reflector boundary.

A sensitivity analysis testing up to 12 energy groups demonstrated that finer energy resolution significantly improves both k_{eff} and power distribution accuracy. As an optimal compromise between computational efficiency and fidelity, the **7-group structure defined in the OECD/NEA C5G7 benchmark** [13] was adopted for this study. This structure (boundaries: 1.36 MeV, 9.2 keV, 55.6 eV, 4.1 eV, 0.63 eV, 0.13 eV) was specifically designed for small cores featuring high leakage and strong heterogeneity, effectively capturing the spectral transitions missed by the 2-group approximation.

3.3. Impact of Homogenization and Transport Approximation

To assess the pin-wise meshing strategy, comparisons were performed between assembly-wise and pin-wise homogenization using both Diffusion and SP_3 solvers on a 2D full-core slice with an explicit reflector. Results in Table I utilize cross-sections (XS) condensed by HELIOS-2 CP.

Table I. 2D FENNECS Results vs. HELIOS-2 Reference (Explicit Reflector, using CP XS)

Parameter (7-Group)	Pin-wise Homogenization		Assembly-wise Homogenization	
	Diffusion	SP_3	Diffusion	SP_3
k_{eff} Difference (pcm)	-902	+375	-970	+309
RMS Pin Power Error (%)	4.148	3.079	–	–
Max Pin Power Error (%)	14.285	11.190	–	–
RMS Assy. Power Error (%)	2.577	1.865	2.827	2.291
Max Assy. Power Error (%)	6.016	4.575	7.255	5.650

Two key trends emerge from the analysis:

1. **Homogenization:** Pin-wise homogenization consistently mitigates errors caused by moderator smearing in distorted lattices. In the assembly-wise model, the largest error occurs in assembly F3, where the homogenization of the missing central pins fails to capture the local flux peaking.
2. **Transport Effects:** The SP_3 approximation significantly improves local accuracy, reducing the RMS pin power error from 4.15% (Diffusion) to 3.08% (SP_3). While Diffusion with CP XS underestimates reactivity (~ -900 pcm), SP_3 provides a more moderate overestimation ($\sim +375$ pcm).

The results are sensitive to the method used in HELIOS, when substituting the MoC solver for CP, the assembly power accuracy improved (RMS error reduced to 1.73% for SP_3), but the reactivity bias shifted. Notably, the diffusion solver combined with MoC XS achieved better reactivity agreement (+82 pcm), whereas the SP_3 solver overestimated k_{eff} by +1097 pcm. Furthermore, the SP_3 diffusion coefficient definition presented a significant trade-off: calculating it via total and self-scattering cross-sections (instead of the standard $1/3\Sigma_{tr}$) improved the power distribution (RMS 2.18%) but yielded an unacceptably high k_{eff} of 1.14977. It should be noted that in all calculations, the diffusion constant is derived from the inverse-weighted transport cross-section generated by HELIOS.

Figure 4 displays the error distribution for the best-estimate case (7-group SP_3 , MoC). The comparison between the reflective boundary case (Left) and the explicit reflector case (Right) clearly identifies the source of error. With the explicit reflector, a strong gradient appears at the core periphery (errors up to $\sim 10\%$). This bias is attributed to the absence of Superhomogenization (SPH) factors or Assembly Discontinuity Factors (ADF) in the current model. While ADF can correct this, their application for the

chosen pin-cell geometry is non-trivial and remains a subject of future work.

Figure 4. Impact of the reflector on FENNECS accuracy (7-Group SP_3 Pin-wise): (Left) 2D Core with Reflective Boundary Conditions; (Right) 2D Core with Explicit Reflector.

3.3.1. Verification of Control Rod Modelling

A specific challenge in the BME TR is the placement of control rods (CRs) in the "cut corners" of the distorted assemblies. In the pin-wise model, the CR material is homogenized into the adjacent corner pin-cell. To verify this approach, a 2D controlled case with both the manual (B_4C) and automatic (Cd) absorbers fully inserted was simulated.

The error statistics for the controlled case using the 7-group SP_3 setup are comparable to those of the uncontrolled results (Mean Absolute Error: 3.10%, RMS: 4.01%, Max: 13.2%). The error topology remains consistent, with the largest deviations still driven by the reflector boundary rather than the absorbers. Although the corner pin-cells containing the strong B_4C absorber are overestimated ($\sim 4\%$), the global error magnitude and distribution are comparable to the uncontrolled state. This consistency confirms that homogenizing the control rods into the distorted corner pin-cells is a valid strategy that conserves absorber worth (k_{eff} bias ≈ -83 pcm) without introducing significant new spatial errors.

3.4. 3D Full-Core Verification

Finally, a 3D FENNECS model was constructed. Cross-sections were generated using the HELIOS-2 CP solver for two different axial slices considering the beam tubes in the reflector regions.

To ensure mathematical consistency, the same fine algebraic mesh was used for both pin-wise and assembly-wise calculations. Both models utilized the SP_3 approximation, since preliminary testing revealed that the diffusion solver consistently underestimates k_{eff} by over 1000 pcm for this high-leakage core. The solver converged in approximately 415 seconds for a system matrix containing over 1.2 million non-zero entries.

The 3D pin-wise k_{eff} is **1.00367** (excess reactivity ≈ 366 pcm). Compared to the SERPENT reference (1.00587 ± 5 pcm), this results in a bias of approximately **-217 pcm**. A comparison of the assembly power errors of the two homogenization schemes is presented in Table II. Local accuracy was assessed via **integral fuel rod powers**, yielding a MARE of **1.465%**, an RMS error of **1.875%**, and a maximum error of **7.451%** at the reflector boundary. The central slices exhibit a spatial error profile similar to the

2D results, characterized by overestimation of pin powers (by $\sim 10\%$) at the reflector boundary. The **axial power profile** shows good agreement (RMS 1.268%), with a maximum local axial difference of 4.14% at the axial reflector boundaries, caused by a power overestimation analogous to that observed in the radial direction.

Table II. 3D Model Summary Metrics for Assembly Power vs. Serpent 2 Reference (Both using SP_3)

Metric	FENNECS Pin-wise	FENNECS Assy-wise	Serpent (Ref.)
Solver	SP_3	SP_3	Monte Carlo
Average relative difference	0.71%	1.08%	–
Maximum relative difference	3.17%	4.23%	–
RMS Assembly Error	0.94%	1.48%	–
Excess reactivity (pcm)	366	706	583 ± 5

Table III details the assembly power distribution. In the assembly-wise model, where error magnitudes are consistent with similar studies [10], the largest error comes from assembly F3 analogous to the 2D problem. Here, the homogenization of the four missing central pins fails to capture local moderator peaking. The pin-wise model significantly mitigates this; the largest remaining deviation (+3.17%) occurs in D5, driven by the void effects of the pneumatic rabbit system.

Table III. 3D Assembly-Averaged Power Error (%) vs. SERPENT 2 Reference

Pin-wise Model (SP_3)					Assembly-wise Model (SP_3)				
0.68	-0.68	-0.85	-1.40	1.09	0.68	-0.91	-2.63	-1.41	-4.23
0.18	-0.61	0.03	-1.10	0.45	1.43	-1.17	0.47	-1.76	0.29
-0.47	-0.08	3.17	0.91	0.82	0.08	0.02	2.69	2.42	0.13
-0.46	-0.72	0.97	-0.48	0.43	0.48	-0.57	0.81	0.48	0.15
	0.04	-0.30	-0.21	0.79		1.17	0.68	0.20	1.06

4. CONCLUSION

This study verified a high-resolution pin-wise modelling strategy for the BME TR, addressing the challenges of its distorted lattices through a novel algebraic meshing algorithm. The analysis demonstrated that accurate deterministic modelling of this small, high-leakage core requires a more refined energy group structure than the typical 2-group one; here, the 7-group structure from the C5G7 benchmark was adopted. Furthermore, the SP_3 transport approximation yields a more consistent pin power distribution and k_{eff} compared to the reference. In the 3D full-core verification, the pin-wise approach outperformed standard assembly-wise homogenization, achieving an assembly power RMS error of 0.94% and an integral fuel rod power MARE of 1.47% with a reactivity bias of -217 pcm. Crucially, the pin-wise model successfully resolved local neutron flux peaking phenomena in the reactor's specific void and water channel regions, which are physically smoothed out in homogenized models. While these results confirm the model's general suitability, future work will specifically investigate the application of SPH factors or ADF to mitigate the observed errors at the reflector boundary prior to the final high-resolution multiphysics coupling with CTF.

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